

1 **Preprint for investigating aquatic biodegradation of pristine and UV-irradiated microplastics from**
2 **conventional and biodegradable agricultural plastics using advanced analytical techniques**

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26

27 **Abstract**

28 There is an increasing tendency to replace conventional agricultural plastic mulching films with
29 biodegradable alternatives. However, while the latter biodegrade well under controlled conditions
30 (e.g. industrial compost), their biodegradation in non-target environments is questioned and poorly
31 understood. Therefore, in this study, microplastics derived from conventional polyethylene (PE) and
32 biodegradable polybutylene adipate terephthalate starch blend (PBAT) mulching films were exposed
33 to UV irradiation and subsequently tested for their ready biodegradability in an aqueous medium. The
34 results showed limited biodegradation for pristine and UV-aged PE: no morphological, surface
35 chemical or internal changes were observed. Pristine PBAT showed signs of initial biodegradation,
36 while UV-aged PBAT biodegraded by up to 57%. New functional groups appeared on the PBAT surface
37 after UV irradiation according to FTIR analysis and crystallinity increased after biodegradation.
38 Elemental analysis revealed a range of metals in PE and PBAT microplastics. No changes in metal
39 distribution analysed in microplastic after UV-aging or biodegradation were found, except that less
40 titanium was present in PBAT after biodegradation indicating potential leaching. None of the PBAT
41 microplastics had ecotoxic effects towards the aquatic plant *Lemna minor*. Pristine and UV-aged PE
42 showed negative effects on roots, but these were not observed after biodegradation. Low
43 biodegradation of pristine PBAT and possible leaching of metals demonstrated here raise questions
44 about the sustainable use of biodegradable alternatives, especially when they enter non-target
45 environments.

46
47 **Keywords:** aging, aquatic ecosystems, compostable plastics, degradation, open environment,
48 microplastics

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53 1. Introduction

54 The production and use of plastics have increased dramatically in recent decades due to their
55 versatility and economic feasibility (PlasticsEurope, 2024). However, this widespread use has come at
56 a significant cost to the environment through extensive pollution of aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems
57 (Ghaffar et al., 2022; Napper and Thompson, 2023; Simul Bhuyan et al., 2021) leading to urgent action
58 to mitigate plastic pollution, with an increasing focus on the development of biodegradable
59 alternatives (Dilshad et al., 2021; Moshood et al., 2022; Rosenboom et al., 2022).

60 In sectors with high plastic consumption, such as agriculture, the transition from conventional plastic
61 to biodegradable is a crucial step in reducing plastic pollution. Unlike conventional plastics,
62 biodegradable alternatives are supposed to be degraded within the soil environment, eliminating the
63 need to collect them after use and minimising agricultural waste. So, the synthesis and production of
64 biodegradable plastics is coupled with testing of their biodegradability in the soil environment
65 (Briassoulis and Dejean, 2010). Many studies have shown that biodegradable plastics may degrade in
66 soil but the degree and rate of this degradation is affected by the composition of the plastics, presence
67 of additives, and the conditions of the surrounding environment such as soil properties, microbial
68 activity, water content, temperature, and also pre-exposure to the UV irradiation (Afshar et al., 2024;
69 Hoshino et al., 2001; Lambert and Wagner, 2017; Liao and Chen, 2021; Mazzon et al., 2022; Oberlintner
70 et al., 2021; Pischedda et al., 2019). A recent study revealed that PBAT mulching film degrades *in situ*
71 in agricultural soil, but after 16 months of burial in soil, the film degradation was still not complete
72 (approximately 66% of the film degraded) and considerable amount of macro- and microplastics was
73 found in soil (Convertino et al., 2024). Field tests tracking the degradation of biodegradable plastics in
74 soil have revealed that the time period for degradation observed in laboratory tests (for certification
75 of biodegradation in soil) are indeed also met in field conditions but only when considering *thermal*
76 days, as opposed to *calendar* days (e.g. Griffin-LaHue et al. (2022)). This highlights an important factor
77 when translating laboratory tests to the field context, where there is a likelihood for biodegradable
78 plastic residues to remain in the soil for several years after use and/or incorporation into soils.

79 Despite extensive research on the biodegradation of plastic alternatives used in the soil environment,
80 there are concerns about their fate once they enter the aquatic environment (Kaing et al., 2024). This
81 is because biodegradable mulching films can fragment due to UV exposure during agricultural use
82 (Convertino et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2022), and the resulting microplastics can be then potentially
83 transferred into water bodies (Ren et al., 2021; van Grinsven and Schubert, 2023). Evidence for the
84 propagation of microplastics from soil environments across wider spatial scales and to connected
85 environments has already been observed (Crossman et al., 2020; Han et al., 2022), demonstrating the
86 potential likelihood for biodegradable in soil plastic fragments to be transferred to aquatic
87 environments. This pathway raises critical questions about the actual biodegradability of these newly
88 synthesised materials in aquatic environments, whose dynamics and consequences differ significantly
89 from those in terrestrial environments.

90 In this context, the aim of this study was to compare and evaluate the biodegradation of two materials
91 used as mulching films — conventional polyethylene (PE) and biodegradable polybutylene adipate
92 terephthalate starch blend (PBAT) — in the aquatic environment (i.e. in ready biodegradability test
93 according to OECD guidelines (OECD, 1992)). To increase environmental relevance, the materials were
94 tested both in their pristine form and after exposure to UV-VIS irradiation as UV light is one of the most
95 common abiotic degradation factors in the environment (Li et al., 2023). Traditionally, the
96 biodegradability of plastics is evaluated by measurement of oxygen consumption or evolved CO₂ (Pires
97 et al., 2022). However, these methods provide limited insight into the degradation process, and
98 therefore we coupled a conventional biodegradability test with advanced analytical techniques to
99 better understand the initial steps of microplastic biodegradation process. The evaluation focused on
100 i) biodegradability in the aquatic environment, ii) morphological changes, iii) surface chemical
101 alterations, iv) changes in elemental composition, v) internal structure modifications, and vi) the
102 changes in ecotoxicity. Understanding biodegradation in non-target environments is crucial to fully
103 assess the impact on the environment and effectively communicate about sustainable practices.

104

105 **2. Material and Methods**

106 *2.1 Characteristics of microplastics*

107 Microplastics were derived from one conventional PE mulch film (internal code M-PEDE-45-black-A0;
108 P6) and one mulch film made of starch and PBAT (internal code M-BIOEL-15-black-A0, P5) within the
109 EU Horizon project PAPHILLONS. Both were black and prepared by cryomilling of the virgin mulching
110 films. Extensive properties of the source material mulching films used for the generation of
111 microplastic and their properties were reported by Hurley et al. (2024). The median size of PE and
112 PBAT were $57 \pm 38 \mu\text{m}$ and $147 \pm 44 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, and they were irregularly shaped fragments
113 (Jemec Kokalj et al., 2024). Organic and inorganic additives were identified in PE and PBAT - these
114 include a series of light stabilisers and antioxidants to slow the degradation of the material, anti-slip
115 agents used for the production of films, and plasticisers to deliver the properties of the mulching film
116 materials (Hurley et al., 2024).

117 A portion of the prepared microplastics was subjected to UV-VIS irradiation to simulate accelerated
118 natural weathering. The samples were carefully placed in glass Petri dishes and shielded by a layer of
119 quartz glass to prevent contamination or possible sample loss during exposure. They were exposed in
120 a Q-SUN Xe-3 UV chamber (Q-Lab, Bolton, UK) for accelerated weathering for 240 hours. The chamber
121 was equipped with three 1800 W Xe lamps calibrated to emit wavelengths corresponding to natural
122 sunlight – xenon arc lamps produce the realistic reproduction of full-spectrum sunlight, including
123 ultraviolet, visible light, and infrared radiation. The samples were irradiated with a power of 40 W/m^2
124 at a chamber temperature of $38 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 50% of relative humidity, while the black standard was
125 maintained at a temperature of $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Throughout the exposure period, the samples were thoroughly
126 mixed and homogenised daily to ensure uniformity and consistency of the aging process. The aged
127 microplastics were labelled as UV-PE and UV-PBAT.

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131 *2.2 Biodegradability in the aquatic environment*

132 In order to comprehensively evaluate the biodegradability of PE, UV-PE, PBAT, and UV-PBAT, two
133 experimental set-ups, i.e., open and closed systems, were used. Both systems were operated under
134 comparable conditions (temperature, stirring, content of nutrients and microorganisms, availability of
135 oxygen, etc.). Details are given in subchapters 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. Microplastics from the open system
136 were then analysed using advanced analytical techniques (subchapter 2.3) to assess the changes due
137 to biodegradation. The closed system was set up to monitor biodegradation as a function of oxygen
138 consumption used for the degradation of microplastics by microorganisms as it is common way how
139 to test biodegradability of polymeric substances (ISO, 2019). A similar approach using open and closed
140 system was successfully applied in our previous study on tire wear particles (Klun et al., 2023).

141

142 *2.2.1 Open system*

143 Artificial freshwater with a low concentration of nutrients and microorganisms (50 mg/L activated
144 sludge) (ISO, 2019) was prepared and 200 mL were added to glass bottles, then 200 mg of microplastics
145 (PE, UV-PE, PBAT or UV-PBAT) were added separately to each bottle to reach the final concentration of
146 1000 mg/L. A blank sample containing only artificial freshwater without the addition of microplastics
147 was also prepared. Two independent replicates of each treatment were performed. The bottles were
148 then placed on a magnetic stirrer, covered with aluminium foil to protect them from light and
149 incubated at 20 ± 2 °C for 28 days. After the test, microplastics (labelled as PE-BIO, PBAT-BIO, UV-PE-
150 BIO, UV-PBAT-BIO) were recovered by filtration (cellulose filters, pore size 7-12 μm , Macherey-Nagel,
151 Germany) and analysed using the methods described in Section 2.3.

152

153 *2.2.2 Closed system*

154 The biodegradability test was also performed in a closed system to assess the degradation of the tested
155 microplastics based on oxygen consumption (ISO, 2019). The test was performed at same time and
156 under comparable conditions as the test in open system, with some minor modifications to meet the

157 requirements of the standard procedure (ISO, 2019). Briefly, the same artificial freshwater was used,
158 and 365 mL was filled into the dark glass bottles. The concentration of microplastics was 100 mg/L, as
159 required by the ISO standard, and microplastic particles (PE, UV-PE, PBAT or UV-PBAT) were added
160 separately to each bottle. In addition, a blank treatment was included, and another treatment was
161 prepared to follow the biodegradation of a reference compound (100 mg/L microcrystalline cellulose,
162 Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Three independent replicates of each treatment were performed. Each bottle was
163 then equipped by rubber cap with KOH and sealed with the OxiTop® head (WTW, Germany). The
164 bottles were then placed on a magnetic stirrer in a climate chamber (20 ± 2 °C, dark) and oxygen
165 consumption was measured for 28 days. The degree of biodegradation was calculated according to the
166 standard procedure (ISO, 2019).

167

168 *2.3 Advanced analytical techniques*

169 Changes in the surface morphology were evaluated using field-emission scanning electron microscopy
170 (FE-SEM) (Section 2.3.1) and surface chemical changes by Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier-
171 transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy (Section 2.3.2). The changes in
172 the elemental composition were studied by laser-ablation inductively coupled plasma mass
173 spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) and prior to LA-ICP-MS, elemental content in each sample was also analysed
174 by conventional digestion followed by liquid ICP-MS (Section 2.3.3). Differential scanning calorimeter
175 (DSC) was used for evaluation of changes in internal structure (i.e., crystallinity) of microplastics
176 (Section 2.3.4).

177

178 *2.3.1 Surface morphology*

179 The surface morphology and shape of microplastics were evaluated by FE-SEM Zeiss ULTRA plus (Zeiss,
180 Germany). Prior to the FE-SEM analysis, the samples were coated with a thin Au/Pd layer.

181

182

183 *2.3.2 Surface chemical changes*

184 To identify surface chemical changes, a FTIR spectrometer (Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer,
185 PerkinElmer, USA) with a Universal ATR module was used. The wavenumber ranged from 4000 cm⁻¹ to
186 450 cm⁻¹, with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ (10 co-scans). Five repetitions for each sample were recorded and
187 averaged. Background and ATR correction of the spectra were applied.

188 The microplastics were also investigated using Raman spectroscopy. The samples were first fixed onto
189 adhesive tape. For the analysis, a confocal Witec Alpha 300R system (WITec, Germany) was used. The
190 laser employed had a wavelength of 532 nm and operated at a power of 0.5 mW. The integration time
191 for each measurement was set to 1 second. We performed 20 accumulations and collected 10 spectra
192 per sample, then calculated the mean values for spectral analysis. The objective lens used had a 50x
193 magnification. Additionally, we utilized an 1800 g/mm grating.

194

195 *2.3.3 Changes in the elemental composition*

196 For LA-ICP-MS analysis, individual samples were mounted in acrylic resin (ClaroCit Kit, Struers, Austria)
197 to investigate the lateral distribution of elements. Cross-sections of these embedded samples were
198 prepared by manual sanding using abrasive paper down to a grain size of 5 μm, and then LA-ICP-MS
199 imaging experiments were carried out similarly as described in previous work (Brunnbauer et al., 2024;
200 Pořízka et al., 2023). LA-ICP-MS analysis was carried out using an imageGEO193 laser ablation system
201 (ESL, USA) operating at a wavelength of 193 nm and equipped with a TwoVol3 ablation chamber. Prior
202 to the analysis, a preablation step was applied to remove potential surface contamination from the
203 sample preparation process.

204 The LA system was coupled to an NexION5000 system (PerkinElmer, USA) using the analytical cup with
205 Tygon® tubing with an inner diameter of 1.6 mm. Samples were ablated under a constant stream of
206 helium (0.8 L/min). Argon was used as a make-up gas (0.86 L/min) and mixed with the sample aerosol
207 using a dual concentric injector (DCI) (ESL, USA) right before the ICP. Kinetic energy discrimination
208 (KED) mode (He) was used to avoid the influence of polyatomic interferences on the measurement.

209 ICP-MS data was recorded using Syngistix 3.5 and LA-ICP-MS data evaluation was carried out using
210 Iolite 4.5.7.1. Data were normalised to ^{13}C to compensate for instrumental drifts. Additional
211 measurement parameters are provided in Table S1.

212 Prior to LA-ICP-MS, elemental content in each sample was also analysed by conventional digestion
213 followed by liquid ICP-MS. Briefly, samples were accurately weighed into PTFE vessels (with an
214 approximate mass of 75 mg). Then 4 mL of concentrated HNO_3 (67 % (w/w), suprapur, Carlo Erba, Italy)
215 and 1 mL of concentrated H_2O_2 (30 % (w/w), pro analysi, Fluka, Honeywell, USA) were added. Acid
216 digestion was performed in a microwave system (Ethos UP, Milestone, Italy) with a three-step
217 temperature program: samples were heated to 210 °C (approx. 7.5 °C/min), the set temperature was
218 maintained for 20 min, and then the samples were allowed to cool down to room temperature.
219 Samples were digested in duplicate. The digested solutions were quantitatively transferred to 20 mL
220 volumetric flasks and diluted to the mark with ultrapure water (resistivity >18.2 M Ω /cm, Synergy
221 Water Purification System, Merck Millipore, Germany). Sample solutions were stored in 50 mL
222 polypropylene centrifuge tubes (Sarstedt, Germany). The blank sample was prepared by the same
223 procedure. For the liquid ICP-MS analysis, samples were diluted by a factor of 10 using 1% HNO_3 .
224 Additionally, 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ Indium was added as an internal standard. Liquid ICP-MS analysis was carried out
225 using an iCAP Q TQ ICP-MS (ThermoFisher Scientific, Germany) in KED mode (additional measurement
226 parameters are provided in Table S2). The instrument was tuned daily for the maximum ^{115}In signal
227 while keeping $^{140}\text{Ce}^{16}\text{O}/^{140}\text{Ce}$ below 1.9 % using Tune A solution (ThermoFisher Scientific, Germany).
228 Metal content for (^{27}Al , ^{56}Fe , ^{39}K , ^{24}Mg , ^{23}Na , ^{60}Ni , ^{208}Pb , ^{47}Ti , ^{68}Zn) was determined using a calibration
229 based on a multielement standard (Multi VIII, Certipur[®], Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and a single
230 element standard for Titanium (Certipur[®], Merck, Darmstadt, Germany).

231

232

233

234

235 2.3.4 Changes in internal structure

236 DSC (DSC 5500 equipped with an RCS 90 cooling system, TA Instruments, USA) was used to determine
237 the melting enthalpy of polymers, which is proportional to their crystallinity. The device was calibrated
238 using the melting enthalpy and melting temperature of water, indium, tin, and lead. The samples were
239 placed into an aluminum pan (Tzero), weighed, and the pan was hermetically sealed to prevent
240 moisture evaporation. This is crucial because moisture evaporation would produce an endothermic
241 peak that could overlap with the melting endotherm, thereby negatively influencing data analysis. The
242 following protocol was applied: heating from 30 °C to 80 °C at a rate of 10 °C per minute, isotherm for
243 2 minutes, heating from 80 °C to 180 °C at 10°C per minute, cooling from 180 °C to 0 °C at 10 °C per
244 minute, and reheating from 0 °C to 180 °C at 10 °C per minute. The measurements were conducted
245 under a nitrogen flow, with samples being measured four times. For the determination of melting
246 enthalpy, the second heating run was used, ensuring the thermal history of the polymer was identical
247 for all samples. The melting enthalpy was determined by integrating the peak area. The obtained
248 energy in Joules, along with the known melting enthalpy of a hypothetical fully crystalline polymer
249 (i.e., 100% crystallinity), was used to determine the crystallinity of measured polymers. Specifically,
250 the melting enthalpy for fully crystalline LDPE is reported as 293 J/g (Niu et al., 2016), and for PBAT, it
251 is 114 J/g (Liu et al., 2022).

252

253 2.4. Ecotoxicity

254 The duckweed *Lemna minor* was selected for an assessment of the ecotoxicity, as it had previously
255 been used for this purpose for microplastics (Boots et al., 2023; Kalčíková et al., 2017; Mateos-
256 Cárdenas et al., 2019; Rozman et al., 2021). The procedure followed the OECD standard method (OECD,
257 2006). Briefly, 50 mL of Steinberg medium was poured into a 100 mL beaker and 100 mg/L of each
258 type of microplastics was added (PE, UV-PE, PE-BIO, UV-PE-BIO, PBAT, UV-PBAT, PBAT-BIO, and UV-PBAT-
259 BIO). A blank sample without microplastics was also prepared. Then 10 fronds of duckweed *Lemna*
260 *minor* with previously removed roots were placed on the water surface. Each treatment was replicated

261 at least four times. The beakers were incubated for seven days in a climate chamber at 25 ± 1 °C and a
262 light/dark scheme of 16/8 h. After incubation, the inhibition of specific growth rate, root length, and
263 chlorophyll content were assessed according to Rozman et al. (2022).

264

265 *2.5. Statistical analysis*

266 The normality and homogeneity of variances were tested with the Shapiro-Wilk test and Levene's test,
267 respectively. Data for the crystallinity were normally distributed and homogeneous, therefore, one-
268 way ANOVA, followed by the Tukey test were used for statistical evaluation. Data for the toxicity testing
269 were not normally distributed, therefore, the Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by the Dunn's test were
270 used for comparisons between control and treatments with microplastics (PE, UV-PE, PE-BIO, UV-PE-
271 BIO, PBAT, UV-PBAT, PBAT-BIO, and UV-PBAT-BIO). All analyses were performed using OriginPro 2023b
272 software (OriginLab Corp., USA) and differences were considered significant if $p < 0.05$.

273

274 **3. Results**

275 *3.1. Biodegradability testing*

276 The biodegradability of pristine (PE, PBAT) and UV-aged (UV-PE, UV-PBAT) microplastics was
277 investigated in a closed system (Figure 1). The reference compound (microcrystalline cellulose)
278 degraded well under the test conditions confirming the suitability of the test set-up. Both PE and UV-
279 PE showed minimal degradation up to 3%. In the case of PBAT, the maximal biodegradation was up to
280 15%, but the UV-aging resulted in increased biodegradation up to 57%.

281

282 **Figure 1.** Biodegradation of a reference compound (microcrystalline cellulose (MC)), pristine (PE and
 283 PBAT) and UV pre-treated microplastics (UV-PE and UV-PBAT) in a closed system. Mean value and
 284 standard deviation are shown.

285

286 3.2. Morphological changes

287 The FE-SEM images of pristine PE, UV-PE, and PE-BIO (Figure 2) showed a comparable smooth surface
 288 with some irregularities, while the surface of UV-PE-BIO was more structured, which may be related
 289 to the attachment of other particulates and microorganisms of the activated sludge. In the case of
 290 PBAT, the images of the surface of PBAT and UV-PBAT were comparable, while the morphology of PBAT-
 291 BIO and UV-PBAT-BIO changed. The surface of PBAT-BIO was smoother compared to PBAT, while UV-
 292 PBAT-BIO also had small holes on the surface.

293

294

295 **Figure 2.** FE-SEM images of pristine microplastics (PE, PBAT), UV-aged microplastics (UV-PE, UV-PBAT)

296 and microplastics after biodegradation (PE-BIO, PBAT-BIO, UV-PE-BIO, UV-PBAT-BIO)

297

298 3.3. Surface chemical changes

299 The surface chemical composition of the microplastics was investigated using ATR-FTIR and Raman

300 spectroscopy. The FTIR spectra of PE, UV-PE, PE-BIO, and UV-PE-BIO are presented in Figure 3A and

301 PBAT, UV-PBAT, PBAT-BIO, and UV-PBAT-BIO in Figure 3B. The main characteristic FTIR bands for PE are

302 clearly visible in all recorded spectra (Figure 3A). They can be assigned as very intense and sharp peaks

303 of CH₂ asymmetric and symmetric stretching around 2915 and 2850 cm⁻¹, intense peak (doublet, due

304 to crystallinity) of CH₂ bending around 1473 and 1463 cm⁻¹, weak deformation modes of CH₂ and CH₃

305 around 1370-1350 cm⁻¹, and medium split CH₂ rocking mode peak at 730 cm⁻¹ and 720 cm⁻¹ (Krimm et

306 al., 1956). According to the FTIR spectra, none of the treatments altered the chemical identity of PE.

307 FTIR spectra of PBAT, UV-PBAT, PBAT-BIO, and UV-PBAT-BIO also showed the main characteristic bands

308 assigned to PBAT polymer (Figure 3B). The absorption band in the region 3000-2800 cm⁻¹ can be

309 ascribed to the C-H stretching region, the very intense and sharp band originating in the region 1750-

310 1680 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the stretching vibration adsorption of the carbonyl group in the ester

311 (C=O stretching of ester groups), the region 1270-1000 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the C-O stretching of

312 ester groups, and around 720 cm⁻¹ a sharp band can be possibly ascribed to the bending vibration

313 adsorption of CH-plane of the benzene ring (Cai et al., 2013). The inserted graph showed the carbonyl
314 region, highlighting the appearance of a weak peak around 1760 cm^{-1} after UV treatment (UV-PBAT
315 and UV-PBAT-BIO), possibly ascribed to modifications induced by the treatment. No other significant
316 changes are recorded after the treatments.

317 Raman spectra of PE, UV-PE, PE-BIO, and UV-PE-BIO and PBAT, UV-PBAT, PBAT-BIO, and UV-PBAT-BIO,
318 are presented in Figure 3C and 3D, respectively. The prominent PE peaks in the Raman spectra were
319 observed as bands due to stretching frequencies of C-H bonds around 3000 cm^{-1} , bending and twisting
320 frequencies of C-H bonds at 1300 and 1400 cm^{-1} , and C-C bond stretching between 1000 and 1200 cm^{-1}
321 $^{-1}$ (Figure 3C) (PhysicsOpenLab, 2022). Pristine PE (PE) showed the highest peak around 3000 cm^{-1} ,
322 followed by PE-BIO, then UV-aged PE and finally the combination of UV and biotic aging. On the other
323 hand, the prominent peaks for PBAT were observed in the Raman spectra at 2927 , 1719 and 1090 cm^{-1}
324 $^{-1}$ (Figure 3D). These peaks correspond to CH_2 and CH_3 vibrations, C=C and C=O stretching, O- CH_2
325 bending modes, =C-H in the benzene ring and out-of-plane =C-H bending modes (de Souza et al., 2022).
326 The peak at 2927 cm^{-1} was the highest in the pristine sample, followed by the combination of biotic
327 and UV-aging (UV-PBAT-BIO), with the lowest signal observed for PBAT-BIO. From the PCA analysis, it
328 is clear that Raman spectroscopy was able to distinguish not only between different types of
329 microplastics, but also between different types of aging (Figure S1).

330

331
 332 **Figure 3.** Results from FTIR analysis for (A) PE and (B) PBAT and Raman spectroscopy for (C) PE and
 333 (D) PBAT.

334

335 3.4 Changes in elemental composition

336 LA-ICP-MS analysis was performed to reveal changes in composition for selected metals based on
 337 liquid ICP-MS analysis of PE and PBAT (Table S3) after UV aging or/and biodegradation. Liquid ICP-MS
 338 revealed the presence of the analysed elements (^{27}Al , ^{56}Fe , ^{39}K , ^{24}Mg , ^{23}Na , ^{60}Ni , ^{208}Pb , ^{47}Ti , ^{68}Zn) in a
 339 concentration ranging from close to detection limits to a few hundred $\mu\text{g/g}$. LA-ICP-MS results showed
 340 that all metals analysed were comparable in all PE treatments (Figures S2-S10), apart from Fe as it
 341 accumulated around the PE particles (Figure S2). In the case of PBAT, the results showed no difference
 342 between the metals analysed in the different treatments (Figure S11-S17), with exception of Ti (Figure
 343 4). Less Ti was present in microplastics indicating potential leaching out of the PBAT after the

344 biodegradability test. Interestingly, PBAT contained Pb, but it was stable in the polymer matrix and was
345 not leached out during UV irradiation or after the biodegradation test (Figure 4).

346

347

348 **Figure 4.** LA-ICP-MS analysis of Ti and Pb in pristine PBAT, UV pre-treated (UV-PBAT) and after
349 biodegradation (PBAT-BIO, UV-PBAT-BIO).

350

351 3.5. Changes in internal structure

352 The changes in the internal structure were evaluated by comparing the crystallinity of the investigated
353 microplastics (Table 1). The crystallinity of PE, UV-PE, PE-BIO and UV-PE-BIO was comparable – none
354 of the treatments changed the internal structure of PE. The crystallinity of pristine PBAT did not change
355 after UV irradiation (UV-PBAT) ($p = 0.5037$). However, crystallinity was significantly increased after
356 biodegradation, as there were statistically significant differences between PBAT and PBAT-BIO ($p <$
357 0.0001) and between UV-PBAT and UV-PBAT-BIO ($p < 0.0001$).

358 **Table 1.** Crystallinity of investigated pristine microplastics (PE, PBAT), after pre-exposure to UV (UV-PE,
 359 UV-PBAT) and after biodegradation (PE-BIO, PBAT-BIO, UV-PE-BIO, UV-PBAT-BIO) (n = 4, mean \pm SD).

Sample	Crystallinity (%)	Sample	Crystallinity (%)
PE	27.4 \pm 0.8	PBAT	16.8 \pm 1.7
UV-PE	28.5 \pm 0.1	UV-PBAT	10.4 \pm 0.5
PE-BIO	29.1 \pm 1.1	PBAT-BIO	59.4 \pm 2.3
UV-PE-BIO	29.4 \pm 0.7	UV-PBAT-BIO	37.0 \pm 14.6

360

361 **3.6. Changes in ecotoxicity**

362 The results of the ecotoxicity tests showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the
 363 specific growth rate of duckweed *Lemna minor* except for pristine PE treatment where specific growth
 364 rate was significantly decreased in comparison to control (Figure 5). Similarly, no statistically significant
 365 differences were found when comparing the effects of microplastics on chlorophyll *a*. However, PE and
 366 UV-PE significantly decreased root growth, but this was no longer observed after biodegradation (PE-
 367 BIO, UV-PE-BIO).

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369

370 **Figure 5.** The effects of pristine microplastics (PE, PBAT), after pre-exposure to UV (UV-PE, UV-PBAT)
 371 and after biodegradation (PE-BIO, PBAT-BIO, UV-PE-BIO, UV-PBAT-BIO) on (A) specific growth rate, (B)
 372 root growth, and (C) chlorophyll *a* content. * Significant difference compared to control ($p < 0.05$). Line

373 – median, square – mean, box – 25–75% of data, whiskers – range within 1.5 inter quartile range,
374 deltoid - outlier.

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376 **4. Discussion**

377 Due to the global plastic crisis, numerous actions have been implemented to mitigate plastic pollution
378 – the most important being the reduction of plastic waste through the widely adopted concepts of
379 reduce, reuse, and recycle (Jia et al., 2019). However, these practices cannot be universally applied, as
380 certain applications require the use of plastics. For example, agriculture relies on the use of plastic
381 mulching films and a shift to the use of biodegradable alternatives such as PBAT has been observed
382 over the previous two decades. Many studies showed that PBAT degrade well in the target
383 environment, i.e., in soil or compost (Kijchavengkul et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2022), but some other
384 studies showed that the degradation in soils is low (Han et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2024) or even reduced
385 when PBAT is blended with other biodegradable polymers e.g. polylactic acid (PLA) (Palsikowski et al.,
386 2018).

387 The results of this study showed that the degradation in a not-target aquatic environment did not
388 occur in pristine PE and UV-aged PE. Similarly, biodegradation of PBAT was low (Figure 1), which is in
389 agreement with the results of a study in which no degradation of pristine PBAT in lake sediments was
390 observed over nine months (van Grinsven and Schubert, 2023) and similarly low degradation of PBAT
391 was evaluated in the marine environment over six months (Lee et al., 2024). In general, lower
392 degradation can be expected in the aquatic environment compared to the soil environment, which is
393 linked to lower microbial activity and nutrient availability (Kaing et al., 2024). For example, our previous
394 study showed fast degradation of chitosan plastic films (both with and without added antioxidants) in
395 different soils (Oberlintner et al., 2021), while the same plastic films were only minimally degraded in
396 the aquatic biodegradability test (Ročnik et al., 2020).

397 On the other hand, pre-exposure of PBAT to UV significantly enhanced its further degradation. FTIR
398 analysis revealed a new absorption band appearing in the carbonyl region of PBAT spectra after UV-

399 aging (see inserted graph in Figure 3B). Additional carbonyl groups are commonly reported in plastic
400 and microplastics after UV-aging and indicate photodegradation (Alavian Petroody et al., 2023; Zidar
401 et al., 2024). In addition, degradation was also visible by SEM as holes appeared on the surface of UV-
402 PBAT after biodegradation (UV-PBAT-BIO, Figure 2). Therefore, it seems that UV-aging improved the
403 ability of microorganisms to degrade PBAT, as the biodegradation of UV-PBAT increased 3.8-times
404 compared to PBAT (Figure 1). Similarly, increased biodegradation in soil was observed for PBAT films
405 after UV-aging (Convertino et al., 2024). However, changes observed for PBAT following biodegradation
406 may also be linked to the more rapid degradation of thermoplastic starch from the starch-PBAT blend,
407 resulting in a relative enrichment of PBAT (Convertino et al., 2024; Pokhrel et al., 2021; Wang et al.,
408 2015). This is relevant as many mulching film applications are expected to be exposed to UV radiation
409 during use on the surface of field soils. But, in regions with low UV intensity, the degradation can be
410 limited as the mulching films contain carbon black, which is used as a photostabiliser (Anunciado et
411 al., 2021). They also contain other stabilisers and antioxidants to slow the degradation of the material
412 (Hurley et al., 2024). Therefore, further work is required to track the progress of degradation of PBAT
413 and its constituent parts, and the corresponding impacts during this biodegradation process.

414 SEM analysis also revealed the presence of some microbial cells on the surface (Figure 2), however, in
415 a smaller amount compared to previous research, where PE fragments were aged in freshwater for 12
416 weeks (Rozman et al., 2023a). This is probably due to the very smooth surface of both PE and PBAT
417 microplastics (Figure 2) as it limits attachment of microorganisms (Rozman et al., 2023b). Agricultural
418 mulch films contains many additives (Hurley et al., 2024) that may also affect biofilm development as
419 they can act toxic limiting the growth of microorganism on the particles surface (Klun et al., 2023). If
420 the biofilm cannot be developed on the plastic surface, the further degradation is likely to be limited
421 (Debroy et al., 2022; Han et al., 2020).

422 Furthermore, LA-ICP-MS revealed alterations in some metals on the PE and PBAT surface. First, it seems
423 that metals within PE are stable, and the only alteration was in the case of Fe which accumulated on
424 the surface of the MPs. On the other hand, the lower content of Ti on PBAT after the biodegradation

425 suggested leaching of Ti into the surrounding environment. Ti is often used as polycondensation
426 catalysts in the production of PBAT so its presence can be expected (Jian et al., 2020). Interestingly,
427 PBAT contained also Pb but the reason or the origin of the Pb is unknown. It has to be noted that the
428 use of highly sensitive LA-ICP-MS helped to reveal the presence of Pb despite the low content
429 measured by to conventional method using acid digestion and liquid ICP-MS (Table S3).

430 The crystallinity of PE and PBAT was not affected by UV irradiation. However, during the biodegradation
431 experiment, whilst the crystallinity of PE remained the same, in PBAT it considerably increased. This
432 may indicate that microorganisms utilise the carbon in amorphous regions which is better accessible
433 (Mohan et al., 2020) but, in this case, it is also plausible that PBAT was hydrolysed in the aquatic
434 medium during the biodegradation experiment as its hydrolysis was previously reported (Deshoules
435 et al., 2022). Monitoring changes in crystallinity is particularly important for low-density plastics as an
436 increase in crystallinity also leads to an increase in density, which in turn can affect the distribution of
437 plastics in the aquatic environment (Budhiraja, 2024).

438 Overall, the morphological, surface and internal changes due to UV irradiation and exposure to
439 microorganisms were minimal. Consequently, no significant changes were also observed in the
440 ecotoxicity of PE and PBAT after biodegradation. In some cases, after biodegradation, the effects of PE
441 were even lowered which is usually related to the smoothing of the MPs surface due to the presence
442 of some microbial cells (Jemec Kokalj et al., 2019). However, further ecotoxicity studies using other
443 aquatic species, like algae, crustaceans, and fish models, would be needed to perform complete hazard
444 assessment of biodegradable microplastics after environmental aging.

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451 **5. Conclusions**

452 Plastics are used in our daily lives and in some cases their use cannot be avoided. Therefore, we need
453 to find a sustainable way to deal with plastics or find alternatives that help to reduce plastic pollution
454 and hazard in the environment. In this context, biodegradable plastics seem to be a good alternative,
455 but their biodegradation must occur efficiently, fast, and with minimal impact on the environment.
456 This should not only refer to the environment in which they are intentionally used, but also to relevant
457 non-target environments, as plastics can also enter ecosystems where their presence was not
458 expected. It is also important to reconsider the use of certain additives that enhance the stability of
459 biodegradable plastics and thus increase their potential persistence in the environment. As shown in
460 our study, certified biodegradable materials intended for use in the soil environment were not
461 degraded in the aquatic environment if they were not first pre-exposed to UV. In the future, it would
462 also be useful to combine conventional biodegradation tests with advanced analytical techniques
463 when assessing the biodegradability of plastics, as these can provide important insights into the
464 degradation and surface changes, the presence of a biofilm, the leaching of elements, changes in
465 internal structure, and ecotoxicity. Together, they provide a comprehensive picture of the initial
466 changes that plastics can undergo in the natural environment, their possible effects and their fate.

467

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486

487 **Data availability**

488 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available on Zenodo under the following
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